

The poultry plight: Exploring farmers' financial awareness and causes of financial distress

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This study explores the awareness and causes of financial distress of poultry farmers in South Africa. The poultry industry faces challenges that can lead poultry farms to a state of financial distress. Internal or external factors can cause financial distress. This paper focuses on the internal factors causing farmers' financial distress. The Morse and Field approach to analyzing qualitative data determined internal financial distress factors. The findings indicate that feed, electricity, labor, management, equipment, and wages are among the internal factors causing poultry farmer's financial distress. The awareness of these internal factors can help poultry farmers prepare for periods of financial distress to avoid bankruptcy. The study contributes to the theoretical and empirical literature on financial distress in the poultry industry and makes recommendations for future researchers.

Keywords: awareness, financial distress, internal factors, poultry farming

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Introduction

The poultry industry is one of South Africa's largest agricultural industries, having progressed from backyard household farming to large-scale commercial production systems over the last century (Marareni 2021). In addition, this industry has emerged as the most commercialized and fastest growing but still faces numerous challenges (Mulaudzi 2019). Disease outbreaks, welfare regulations, food safety, house environment, and several issues linked to nutrition and feeding are among current and future challenges to the poultry industry (Nkukwana 2018). Further, agriculture finance is essential for meeting long-term agricultural needs and short-term needs such as hiring labor, implementing modern technology, improving efficiency, implementing marketing strategies, and dealing with risks (Omobitan & Khanal 2022). The poultry industry's low performance is due to farmers' inadequate financial management techniques (Paul 2015). These negatively influence the business's employees, shareholders, lenders, and other stakeholders (Madhushani & Kawshala 2018). Chapter 6 of the Companies Act (no. 71 of 2008) defines a business as financially distressed when it appears reasonably unlikely to be able to pay its debts

within six months of being due and payable. According to Gerber (2020), businesses fail without much warning, and the measure put in place for predicting financial distress leaves stakeholders with a deficiency of information. Businesses fail because they lack awareness of the cause of the problem, and the measures need to be clearer. This study aimed to explore poultry farmers' awareness regarding causes of financial distress. Determining the causes affecting poultry production profitability is essential for the farmers' economic progress and may contribute to the development of public and private policies (Mendes et al. 2014). The literature review, methodology, results, discussion and findings, discussion, and conclusion are presented in the next sections.

Literature Review

Business management plays an important role in business profitability because it involves efficiently managing scarce resources to produce valuable output, thus resulting in higher profit margins (Venter 2019). Financial management involves acquiring a business's necessary funds, investing for a higher return, and continuously managing profitability, liquidity, and solvency (Marx & Mpofu 2019). It is emphasized that financial management assists in making decisions that maximize the business value and, therefore, one of the most important agricultural management functions (Jayashree & Priya 2016). It is crucial in farming business, regardless of type or size (Standard bank agribusiness SA 2013). A successful farm is managed like a business; without proper management, no farm can function successfully (Du Plessis 2019). The agricultural industry is critical for poverty alleviation, ensuring food security, accelerating rural development and creating jobs (Christiaensen & Martin 2018). Further, agriculture is a capital-intensive industry, with most existing farm-type asset structures dominated by investments in farmland, buildings, machinery, equipment, and livestock breeding (Kusi et al. 2015). The agriculture industry in South Africa produces a wide range of products, from beef and poultry to maize, fruit, and vegetables (Stats SA 2021). Popular agriculture products in South Africa include citrus and deciduous fruits, maize (corn), grapes, oilseeds, wheat, dairy products, sugarcane, meat, tobacco, wine, and wool.

Financial distress can be defined as the inability of businesses to satisfy their monetary obligations according to the agreements made between them and their supply chain partners (Lu et al. 2020.) Although financial distress does not necessarily imply that the distressed business will ultimately fail, a significant and persistent decline in a business's financial performance may eventually result in bankruptcy, making investors and creditors suffer considerable financial loss (Habib et al. 2020). The causes of financial distress are numerous and cannot be listed entirely (Susesti & Wahyuningtyas 2020). According to the financial theory, the factors causing financial distress can occur due to the influence of the business's internal and external factors. Internal factors of financial distress are the primary and most influential factors in financial distress (Mahtani & Garg 2018). Further, internal causes of financial distress refer to failures within management's control (Lukason & Hoffman 2014). Cash flow difficulties are a common internal factor of financial distress (Yadiati 2018). According to Muthoni (2018), inadequate capital, poor succession planning, corporate governance, and large debts are internal causes of financial distress. Memba and Job (2013) add that poor management skills and qualities, low productivity and profitability, and illiquidity are among the internal factors that cause financial distress. Njogo (2011) further adds that unwise expansion, poor financial management, and size are internal causes of financial distress.

The awareness of the financial distress condition of a business from an early age will give room for the business to formulate plans and take corrective actions to monitor and anticipate conditions that lead to bankruptcy (Susesti & Wahyuningtyas 2020). Awareness is an important tool for studying the attitude and behavior of people. Awareness can be defined as the state or capacity to see, feel, or be aware of occasions, objects, or tactile patterns (Gafoor 2012). Businesses become aware of the severity of financial issues later when little can be done to correct them (Mahtani & Garg 2018). They need to be made aware

of the critical factors to focus on and ignore the warning signs. Their awareness (or lack thereof) is an essential property of their epistemic states, with significant consequences for their actions (Hill 2010). Poultry farming is distinguished commercially by higher capital and labor requirements, poor financial management practices, and a scarcity of modern financial support tools (Folajinmi & Peter 2020). Northern Cape and North-West provinces are home to the largest number of birds (broiler and layer), with the Northern Cape at 22 percent of the national total and the North-West province at 21 percent (SAPA 2019).

Methodology

This study implemented a qualitative research approach with an exploratory research design. A qualitative description strategy was adopted because little was known about whether poultry farmers know about financial distress and its causes. One of the characteristics of a qualitative description design is that its implementation seeks a straightforward description of the data, limiting researchers' interpretations and focusing on the participants' views instead (Sandelowski 2000). The study was conducted in the North West province of South Africa. The North-West province represents 20 percent of the arable land in the country. It is a highly productive agricultural area with key role players in the poultry industry, making it ideal for this study.

The study population comprised broiler and layer poultry farmers with five to 54 years of experience in the poultry industry. Non-probability convenience sampling was used to select participants. Data was gathered by conducting in-depth interview sessions culminating in a total sample size of 12 participants when data saturation was reached. Because the participants were a homogeneous sample, there is, in this respect, compliance with Young and Casey's (2019, p53) recommendation that six to ten interviews are sufficient for data collection. The study's objectives were explained, and consent to partake in the study was provided by all participants prior to commencing the interview sessions. The interviewer also indicated that the study had ethical clearance.

A well-connected liaison, who knew the farmers on an informal basis, assisted in identifying the participants. This person also mediated the recruitment of farmers and discussed the process based on the informed consent principles. The selected farmers were asked permission to conduct the interviews. Further, the liaison ensured that the farms were suitable for the study. The interviews were held in person for approximately 20 minutes. In addition, the person organized the interviews on the farm or a convenient place for the farmer. An interview guide was devised with sections comprising questions relative to the objectives of this study. The interview sessions were audio recorded, after which a professional transcription agency transcribed the recordings. Data were analyzed using the four steps of Morse and Field's (1996) qualitative data analysis: comprehending, synthesizing, theorizing, and re-contextualizing the data. The ATLAS.ti 22 software was used to code the data and assist in identifying relevant categories and developing suitable themes. Trustworthiness was confirmed by considering the criteria proposed by Guba (1981) to ensure credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability.

Results

Results indicate that *feed* may be an internal cause of financial distress in the poultry industry. The results indicate that feed costs have remained a considerable challenge in the poultry industry. Feed costs (energy and protein contents) have a significant impact on poultry farm profitability because chickens require different nutrients (feed) depending on their type, age, and sex (Kusi et al. 2015). Feed costs for poultry production are high in South Africa, with small-scale producers paying R50 to R100 more for a bag of feed than commercial producers (Nkukwana 2018). *Labor* could be an internal cause of financial distress. The availability of sufficiently skilled persons is a significant challenge such as mechanics, electricians, and boilermakers. Contrary to the expected findings on the reliability of labor being an

internal cause of financial distress, some poultry farmers posited that labor is not much of a problem because they have a small hostel for their laborers. *Electricity* is also an internal cause of financial distress. Table 1 shows a summary of the basic parameters required for each of the cycles.

Table 1. Basic Parameters Required for Each Stage of the Cycle

Cycle stage	Temperature (Centigrade)	Light cycle (hour)	Illumination Intensity (lx)
1 st	24-25	24	20
2 nd	20-25	16-18	20
3 rd	20-25	23	20

Source: Adapted from Sierocka et al. (2023)

Without electricity, poultry farms cannot function. The cost of electricity was indicated as a considerable challenge in poultry farms. It was found that the cost of electricity is a financial problem on the farm. The availability of electricity was also reported as a problem in poultry farms. In the first week of rearing, 24-hour lighting is used, then the daylight is gradually shortened to 16–18 hours, and in the period from 36 to 49 days, a 23 hours light cycle is used (Sierocka et al. 2023). The total energy demand for broiler production in modern farms is 53 kWh per broiler per year, considering the entire production process (Amini et al. 2015). *Management* also causes internal financial distress in the poultry industry. The results indicate poor management is related to financial distress, resulting in indecision, resource allocation distortion, and distress in integrating and achieving business goals (Zhou, 2019). Poor management skills and qualities could cause financial distress in a business as it reduces the ability to develop sound plans and strategies for effective management. It was found that good management could help solve most labor-related issues. There is an indication that management is an essential factor in any business. The erroneous management decision was reported as a factor that can result in the perusal of efficient and effective options that can lead to a lower return on the poultry farm. Poor management is innately linked to other internal causes of financial distress since they have complete control over factors in the microenvironment. Figure 1 depicts the causes of financial distress—generated using the network's function in ATLAS.ti 22—which indicates the interactions between the variables as concluded through the interpretation of interviews' transcriptions.

Figure 1. Network Summary of the Interactions between Factors of Financial Distress

Source: the authors

Faulty *equipment* and equipment maintenance are challenges on the farm, leading to financial distress.

Equipment breakages can negatively affect the entire program on the poultry farm. Equipment is a major part of the functioning of the farm, and proper and well-maintained equipment has to be used for the successful functioning of the farm. Electrical equipment, which constitutes the operational systems in agricultural production, mainly includes lighting systems, ventilation systems, and livestock support systems, such as drinkers, milking machines, feeders, or room cleaning systems (Sierocka et al. 2023). Electricity is related to this internal source of financial distress in that electricity is likely to exacerbate equipment costs. Finally, high *wages* cause some laborers to be retrenched. As a result, the farm could suffer financial distress due to a lack of staff. Impacts of minimum wages may occur over the long term (Kandilov & Kandilov 2020). In the long term, small farms become unviable, and overall, the industry experiences fewer, larger, and more capital-intensive farms (Piek et al. 2020). Naturally, wages are related to labor and, to a lesser degree, management. Compensation costs likely aggravate the degree to which labor and management cause financial distress.

Discussion

The aim of this study was to explore awareness and causes of financial distress of poultry farmers. The poultry industry experiences internal and external causes of financial distress. This paper focuses on the internal factors causing poultry farmers' financial distress. Unresolved financial distress can result in a business being bankrupt or closing down due to financial implications. Knowing these factors causing financial distress is important because poultry farmers will become better prepared for financial distress. The poultry industry contributes to the country's GDP, alleviates poverty, and creates employment opportunities. It also contributes to the agricultural industry. Poultry farmers need to be made aware of the factors that could potentially lead their farms to financial distress and closure of their farms, which could, directly and indirectly, affect the country's GDP and economy. The poultry farmers' awareness of the causes of financial distress could assist in the overall profitability of the poultry farm. With proper financial management, proper farm functioning can be guaranteed.

Feed, labor, electricity, management, equipment, and wages are internal factors causing financial distress. In farms, poor management of staff, resources, and finances can negatively affect the farm's financial health in the long run. High feed costs have been a constant challenge in the poultry industry. Electricity and its unreliability in South Africa are internal causes of financial distress. Affluent farmers have the means to switch to alternative sources. High electricity costs negatively affect poultry farms' finances. Poultry farms need lights, and ventilation systems for the proper and efficient functioning of poultry farms, requiring constant electricity. The results indicate that skilled laborers are important in successfully running a poultry farm. Skilled laborer is a concern. Another challenge is wage, especially the minimum wage, and its influence on workers and employers. High wages result in workers being retrenched, which could lead to a farm lacking staff and later experiencing financial difficulties. Thriving farmers can offer higher wages. Equipment can also be considered an internal factor. Renewing and maintaining equipment is a necessity on any farm. To ensure efficiency in a poultry farm, there is a need for proper and well-functioning equipment. Without proper equipment, the poultry farm will likely be unable to reach set targets on time. The cost of renewing and maintaining equipment is a concern that influences poultry farms' finances. The results of this study will raise awareness of the internal causes of financial distress in poultry farms and the importance of being prepared for times of financial distress. Identifying these causes may also support establishing strategies to improve poultry farming profitability (Mendes et al. 2014). Without proper preparedness measures, poultry farmers will have their farms closed due to financial implications.

Although the study was planned and successfully conducted, several limitations were identified. Firstly, the resulting sample size was considerably small due to selecting a feasible and appropriate qualitative approach. Secondly, the literature about the causes of financial distress needs to be more

extensive, especially within the poultry industry in South Africa. Thirdly, the study results are based on the data gathered from farmers residing in the North-West province of South Africa. Therefore, this study's findings differ when data is gathered from other provinces in South Africa or other countries. The authors recognize that the poultry farming laws are different in different countries, hence different results.

Further research studies could consider gathering data from other geographical areas (provinces or countries), including larger samples of farmers, and be extended to other agriculture industries. Therefore, explore the awareness and causes of financial distress in the agricultural industry. Future researchers can incorporate a mixed-method design, including qualitative and quantitative research methods, to triangulate various data sources.

Conclusion

Common challenges faced in the poultry industry include high input costs, high-quality feed costs, poor financial management, inefficient management, disease and parasite, housing, marketing problems, and inability to export. According to the findings of this study, the internal factors that cause financial distress are feed, management, labor, equipment, and electricity. The high feed cost can be addressed through government interventions such as providing subsidies for feed and other poultry inputs to aid the farmers and promote food security. Financial management is crucial in any business; it allows owners to achieve goals such as profitability and sustainability. Therefore, financial management in agriculture is just as important as any other industry. In addition, adaptability and resilience in agriculture are essential for sustainable business success. Poultry farm profitability could be affected due to poor financial management practices. Poultry farmers can use financial distress as an early warning sign before their farm business enters bankruptcy. To enhance the effectiveness of their contingency plans, farmers need to be aware of the prominent causes of financial distress. These plans include having standby generators, cash reserves, backup water supply systems, and good supplier relationships. Stakeholders of the poultry industry in developing countries can use this study as a starting point for advancing proactive actions to mitigate the occurrence and impact of internal financial distress factors. The awareness of internal causes that result in financial distress can assist the poultry farmer in preparing and avoiding them entirely. In addition, improved financial management will ensure that causes such as feed labor, electricity, equipment, and wages can be handled in such a way as to ensure sustainability. Further, efficient financial management can also ensure long-term success and food security. The development of financial skills and the awareness thereof is also crucial in the agriculture industry.

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